

Supporting information

MS title: An evaluation of pool-sequencing transcriptome-based exon capture for population genomics in non-model species

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Figure S1: Cumulative base sequencing depth for each of the 24 genomic libraries. The libraries for the 23 individuals are represented in grey and the pool library is shown in black. A and B show exactly the same data, with different scales for the x-axis.

Figure S2: New method for predicting intron-exon boundaries (IEB) by mapping genomic reads directly onto CDS sequences and by counting, at each position, the number of reads beginning or ending at that position (nbBE). Two cases are illustrated here: on the left, when the reads stop mapping to the exact position of the exon end for the two exon ends of one IEB; on the right, when the reads stop mapping to some bases of the exon end for one of the two exon ends. The latter case is possible when the beginning of the intron is, by chance, similar to the beginning of the next exon. This can occur for both exon ends, which increases the length of the IEB prediction region (the + region).

Figure S3: Mapping of genomic reads directly onto targeted CDS (concatenation of exons) visualized in Integrative Genomics Viewer (IGV). Reads begin or end next to an intron-exon boundary (IEB), with the possible alignment of the intron with some bases. Here, the first intron base (G) can be aligned with the first base of the exon N+1 (G), and the last two bases of the intron (AG) can be aligned with the end of exon N (AG). In total, sequencing depth is abnormally overestimated for three bases located next to this IEB (AG//G) in the CDS.

Figure S4: **A.** Mean sequencing depth (plus or minus standard error) for the 23 individual libraries, plotted as a function of position along the *HA_10038* coding sequence (960 bp; concatenation of 8 exons). The sequencing depth at the exon ends was overestimated, as explained in Figure S2. **B.** Mean exon sequencing depth as a function of exon length ($n = 6,293$ complete exons ≥ 20 bp) for pool data. **C.** Mean binned sequencing depth at the ends of 200-500 bp complete exons ($n = 2,729$ exons) for pool data. We used 10-base pair bins, with five bins for the 5' and 3' ends.

Figure S5:

Comparison of the mean sequencing depth of targeted CDS between the two capture methods, *i.e.* between the pool and individuals. Each cross corresponds to a CDS target. Note: 4 out-of-range CDS targets were discarded from the analysis for the purposes of representation.

Figure S6: Example of a false SNP called next to an exon end (or intron-exon boundary (IEB)) when reads were mapped directly onto the target CDS. Partial IGV screenshot. Here, the beginning of the intron sequence is very similar to the first five bases of the next exon sequence in the CDS. Thus, genomic reads with the end of exon N and the start of the intron can align with the end of exon N and the start of exon N+1 over five bases. This creates an abnormally inflated estimate of sequencing depth locally for five bases at the boundary of exon N+1. An SNP is detected when the two sequences are not strictly identical, as in this example.

<i>Library Name</i>	<i>Number of read pairs</i>	<i>Mbases</i>	<i>Proportion of reads (%)</i>	<i>Number of cleaned read pairs</i>	<i>Number of cleaned reads (SE1 only)</i>	<i>Number of cleaned reads (SE2 only)</i>	<i>Total number of cleaned reads</i>	<i>Proportion of read retained (%)</i>
Pool of 36 non-indexed individuals	186998614	56100	50,2	156104105	26592490	1700304	340501004	91,0
23 indexed individuals (subtotal)	185457659	55637	49,8	156088966	23928203	2421740	338527875	91,3
<i>Individual 1</i>	7241970	2173	1,94	6029132	1045507	70861	13174632	91,0
<i>Individual 2</i>	7484575	2245	2,01	6202580	1099934	74390	13579484	90,7
<i>Individual 3</i>	8732346	2620	2,34	7237004	1300459	83530	15857997	90,8
<i>Individual 4</i>	7668116	2300	2,06	6353240	1138260	76576	13921316	90,8
<i>Individual 5</i>	7738008	2321	2,08	6420474	1139591	77887	14058426	90,8
<i>Individual 6</i>	7637178	2291	2,05	6332647	1122654	77082	13865030	90,8
<i>Individual 7</i>	8391493	2517	2,25	6943476	1256004	81538	15224494	90,7
<i>Individual 8</i>	6912561	2074	1,86	5474368	1285154	64563	12298453	89,0
<i>Individual 9</i>	7811654	2343	2,10	6564169	903887	147683	14179908	90,8
<i>Individual 10</i>	9149586	2745	2,46	7932068	972713	95969	16932818	92,5
<i>Individual 11</i>	8531966	2560	2,29	7074679	1060746	155945	15366049	90,0
<i>Individual 12</i>	7875656	2363	2,11	6306581	747908	508170	13869240	88,1
<i>Individual 13</i>	7974834	2392	2,14	6902758	871979	79481	14756976	92,5
<i>Individual 14</i>	7762438	2329	2,08	6636308	933444	79203	14285263	92,0
<i>Individual 15</i>	7504558	2251	2,01	6469430	839092	77207	13855159	92,3
<i>Individual 16</i>	8987541	2696	2,41	7771107	1002259	91165	16635638	92,5
<i>Individual 17</i>	8071329	2421	2,17	6904584	966861	75809	14851838	92,0
<i>Individual 18</i>	8371274	2511	2,25	7028527	1140522	86402	15283978	91,3
<i>Individual 19</i>	7629129	2289	2,05	6561116	877072	78807	14078111	92,3
<i>Individual 20</i>	7726175	2318	2,07	6526912	1014177	77100	14145101	91,5
<i>Individual 21</i>	8405897	2522	2,26	7174677	1045475	78480	15473309	92,0
<i>Individual 22</i>	9176292	2753	2,46	7805586	1145586	90937	16847695	91,8
<i>Individual 23</i>	8673083	2602	2,33	7437543	1018919	92955	15986960	92,2
Total	372456273	111737	100	312193071	50520693	4122044	679028879	91,2

Table S1: Summary statistics for the raw sequence data obtained for the 24 libraries

LibraryName	Total number of cleaned reads	Mb (cleaned reads)	unmapped reads	Reads aligned not properly or not on only one target			Reads aligned properly (*) on only one target			Number of mapped read pairs			Orphan mapped reads			Number of Mb of mapped read that can be aligned			median read alignment length (pb)	mean read alignment length (pb)	min		max	%of reads that mapped on their entire length
				%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%			%	%		
Pool of non-indexed 36 individuals	340501004	47879	43807484	12.9	11961756	3.5	284731764	83.6	124044982	77.2	36641801	22.8	35926	75.0	144	126.2	21	194	62.7					
23 indexed individuals (subtotal)	338527875	47564	47298784	14.0	11459979	3.4	280467456	82.8	122895052	78.4	33938762	21.6	35315	74.2	144	126.3	21	194	62.7					
Individual 1	13174632	1857	1727954	13.1	389241	3.0	11755781	89.2	4857144	78.8	1302903	21.2	1397.7	75.3	144	126.9	21	190	62.3					
Individual 2	13579484	1912	1912219	14.1	442293	3.3	11224972	82.7	4932128	78.4	1360716	21.6	1419.9	74.3	144	126.6	21	184	62.2					
Individual 3	15857997	2234	2060717	13.0	513572	3.2	13283708	83.8	5852549	78.8	1578610	21.2	1685.0	75.4	144	126.9	21	184	62.2					
Individual 4	13921316	1963	1817460	13.1	446801	3.2	11657055	83.7	5148113	79.1	1360829	20.9	1477.6	75.3	144	126.8	21	181	61.5					
Individual 5	14058426	1983	1842578	13.1	460067	3.3	11755781	83.6	5182201	78.8	1391379	21.2	1490.6	75.2	144	126.9	21	183	61.8					
Individual 6	13865030	1952	1784540	12.9	445871	3.2	11634619	83.9	5120592	78.6	1393435	21.4	1473.9	75.5	144	126.8	21	181	61.9					
Individual 7	15224494	2146	2064586	13.6	486293	3.2	12673615	83.2	5581393	78.7	1510829	21.3	1607.3	74.9	144	126.9	21	185	62.0					
Individual 8	12298453	1730	1585884	12.9	371706	3.0	10340863	84.1	4472482	76.2	1395899	23.8	1310.1	75.7	144	126.8	21	185	60.9					
Individual 9	14179908	1956	2072547	14.6	471677	3.3	11635684	82.1	5091130	77.8	1453424	22.2	1444.8	73.9	143	124.2	21	190	63.6					
Individual 10	16932818	2382	2545433	15.0	627331	3.7	13760054	81.3	6045511	78.4	1669032	21.6	1733.7	72.8	144	126.1	21	194	63.2					
Individual 11	15366049	2107	2449822	15.9	531803	3.5	12384424	80.6	5270579	74.1	1843266	25.9	1530.3	72.6	143	123.6	21	180	64.3					
Individual 12	13869240	1922	2064938	14.9	474583	3.4	11329719	81.7	4843138	74.7	1643443	25.3	1413.5	73.6	144	124.8	21	186	64.0					
Individual 13	14756976	2079	2127230	14.4	526246	3.6	12103500	82.0	5337625	78.9	1428250	21.1	1529.5	73.6	144	126.4	21	183	63.3					
Individual 14	14285263	2013	1975586	13.8	504009	3.5	11805668	82.6	5189804	78.4	1426060	21.6	1492.8	74.2	144	126.5	21	190	63.1					
Individual 15	13855159	1950	1973303	14.2	504201	3.6	11377655	82.1	5002107	78.5	1373441	21.5	1435.4	73.6	144	126.2	21	181	63.2					
Individual 16	16635638	2348	2346627	14.1	581732	3.5	13707279	82.4	6091118	80.0	1525043	20.0	1739.6	74.1	144	127.0	21	186	63.5					
Individual 17	14851838	2087	2136572	14.4	518154	3.5	12197112	82.1	5377092	78.8	1442928	21.2	1538.4	73.7	144	126.2	21	187	63.0					
Individual 18	15283978	2154	2081198	13.6	494861	3.2	12707919	83.1	5618944	79.3	1470031	20.7	1610.5	74.8	144	126.8	21	183	62.1					
Individual 19	14078111	1984	1994794	14.2	503180	3.6	11580137	82.3	5108075	78.9	1363987	21.1	1462.5	73.7	144	126.4	21	182	62.8					
Individual 20	14145101	1993	1959427	13.9	479115	3.4	11706559	82.8	5167455	79.0	1371649	21.0	1479.8	74.3	144	126.5	21	183	62.2					
Individual 21	15473309	2183	2142096	13.8	527369	3.4	12803844	82.7	5672944	79.6	1457956	20.4	1621.9	74.3	144	126.7	21	188	62.6					
Individual 22	16847695	2375	2377652	14.1	610065	3.6	13859978	82.3	6093890	78.5	1672198	21.5	1751.8	73.8	144	126.5	21	188	62.8					
Individual 23	15986960	2256	2255621	14.1	549809	3.4	13181530	82.5	5839038	79.5	1503454	20.5	1669.0	74.0	144	126.7	21	187	62.8					
Total	679028879	95444	91106268	13.4	23421735	3.4	565199220	83.2	246940034	77.8	70580563	22.2	71242	74.6	144	126.3			62.7					

Table S2: Raw mapping data for all 24 libraries

TARGET BASE LEVEL								GLOBAL TARGET LEVEL				
Library Name	Nb bases with no read	Nb of bases with at least one read		Mean base sequencing depth	Median base sequencing depth	Number of base with sequencing depth <300X and <7000X for individuals and pool respectively		Nb targets with no read	Number of targets with at least one read		Mean target sequencing depth	Median target sequencing depth
		%	%			%	%					
Pool of non-indexed 36 individuals	326294	5021167	93.9	6634.8	3361	4795633	89.7	500	5217	91.3	7033.0	3324
Individual 1	351465	4995996	93.4	239.3	119	4854127	90.8	545	5172	90.5	254.9	119
Individual 2	348242	4999219	93.5	262.2	131	4827714	90.3	537	5180	90.6	278.9	130
Individual 3	346493	5000968	93.5	311.2	152	4709553	88.1	540	5177	90.6	331.2	154
Individual 4	347151	5000310	93.5	272.9	139	4801695	89.8	542	5175	90.5	291.2	139
Individual 5	347769	4999692	93.5	275.2	140	4788898	89.6	544	5173	90.5	292.8	140
Individual 6	349565	4997896	93.5	272.1	137	4786866	89.5	545	5172	90.5	291.6	140
Individual 7	346194	5001267	93.5	296.7	149	4745769	88.7	543	5174	90.5	315.5	149
Individual 8	348816	4998645	93.5	241.9	122	4852703	90.7	545	5172	90.5	257.6	122
Individual 9	347880	4999581	93.5	266.8	135	4819917	90.1	540	5177	90.6	280.6	134
Individual 10	348145	4999316	93.5	320.0	162	4671124	87.4	536	5181	90.6	338.9	160
Individual 11	345535	5001926	93.5	282.5	139	4782468	89.4	548	5169	90.4	295.9	141
Individual 12	347692	4999769	93.5	260.9	128	4823433	90.2	544	5173	90.5	275.6	130
Individual 13	345963	5001498	93.5	282.4	140	4785941	89.5	533	5184	90.7	300.9	142
Individual 14	348232	4999229	93.5	275.6	138	4807067	89.9	544	5173	90.5	291.9	138
Individual 15	348292	4999169	93.5	264.9	134	4813076	90.0	544	5173	90.5	280.8	133
Individual 16	347384	5000077	93.5	321.2	157	4662713	87.2	543	5174	90.5	341.2	158
Individual 17	347555	4999906	93.5	284.0	144	4771824	89.2	541	5176	90.5	300.4	144
Individual 18	350460	4997001	93.4	297.4	148	4730760	88.5	547	5170	90.4	317.4	150
Individual 19	348109	4999352	93.5	269.9	138	4802299	89.8	547	5170	90.4	285.9	137
Individual 20	348670	4998791	93.5	273.2	139	4801834	89.8	543	5174	90.5	289.9	139
Individual 21	346829	5000632	93.5	299.5	151	4741120	88.7	546	5171	90.4	317.0	151
Individual 22	347987	4999474	93.5	323.3	165	4638896	86.7	543	5174	90.5	343.7	165
Individual 23	349634	4997827	93.5	308.1	156	4713310	88.1	544	5173	90.5	328.3	156
Considering all 24 libraries	323418	5024043	94.0	13136	6662	4796032	89.7	491	5226	91.4	12738.3	6331.0

Table S3: Raw results for capture efficiency per target for all 24 libraries

Library Name	Correctly aligned reads	Number of duplicates	%
Pool of 36 non-indexed individuals	284731764	273926275	96,2
23 indexed individuals (subtotal)	279728866	185312226	66,2
<i>Individual 1</i>	11017191	7141232	64,8
<i>Individual 2</i>	11224972	7285322	64,9
<i>Individual 3</i>	13283708	9043890	68,1
<i>Individual 4</i>	11657055	7562879	64,9
<i>Individual 5</i>	11755781	7705899	65,5
<i>Individual 6</i>	11634619	7581803	65,2
<i>Individual 7</i>	12673615	8488778	67,0
<i>Individual 8</i>	10340863	6572290	63,6
<i>Individual 9</i>	11635684	7569467	65,1
<i>Individual 10</i>	13760054	9338775	67,9
<i>Individual 11</i>	12384424	8214520	66,3
<i>Individual 12</i>	11329719	7347433	64,9
<i>Individual 13</i>	12103500	7972917	65,9
<i>Individual 14</i>	11805668	7760721	65,7
<i>Individual 15</i>	11377655	7384171	64,9
<i>Individual 16</i>	13707279	9442127	68,9
<i>Individual 17</i>	12197112	8058067	66,1
<i>Individual 18</i>	12707919	8588109	67,6
<i>Individual 19</i>	11580137	7506713	64,8
<i>Individual 20</i>	11706559	7684259	65,6
<i>Individual 21</i>	12803844	8592530	67,1
<i>Individual 22</i>	13859978	9530119	68,8
<i>Individual 23</i>	13181530	8940205	67,8

Table S4: Number of reads scored as duplicates for the 24 libraries.